

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL HOUSING CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: The most developing type of construction in recent years is housing. Despite its apparent safety in environmental terms, on a large scale it poses no less a threat, and sometimes even greater, than industrial construction.

Key words: urban planning, ecological housing, problems and development prospects.

Introduction. Ecological housing construction solves the main social problem - providing the population with housing [1, 2]. However, as anthropogenic pressure on land and resources increases, society is increasingly aware of the specific impact of large-scale housing construction on the quality of the natural environment. The scale of housing construction can be very different - from a residential microdistrict to an entire city (at the top of this scale of scale are residential areas of large cities).

Modern urban planning in the Republic of Uzbekistan is in a state of unstable transitional development [3, 6, 7, 8]. Soviet-style centralized state planning ceased to exist, and therefore cities lost their previous economic base in the form of sectoral and territorial planning of financial and territorial development resources. The new urban planning system is not taking shape very systematically and is far from complete [5, 6, 9]. Local city budgets, spent on current payments and capital investments, are experiencing a huge deficit. The consequence of this was both a massive reduction in public investment in housing and communal construction, and chronic non-payment of wages in the public services sector, financed from local budgets [11, 12].

The strategic goal of modern state housing policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to create a market of affordable and comfortable housing that meets the housing needs of the bulk of the population, and to create mechanisms for state participation in supporting the development and functioning of this market [10, 13, 14]. That is why the inclusion of the task of forming an affordable housing market and providing comfortable living conditions for citizens of Uzbekistan among the priority national projects, along with the development of education, healthcare and rural areas, determines the social orientation of the new stage of economic transformation in the country [15, 16].

The characteristics of the comfort of the living environment play a significant role in the value orientations of people, directly and indirectly influencing their behavior, which in turn significantly affects social development. However, in our opinion, we should not talk about the attractiveness of the home, but about the degree of favorableness of the psychophysiological impact of the entire environment, not just residential spaces. Unfortunately, it has not yet been possible to develop clear and unambiguous criteria in this area, although certain patterns can be traced. Thus, we can say with a fair degree of confidence that the experience of mass housing construction of the Soviet era, starting with Khrushchev's "achievements" and up to our time, has led to unfavorable consequences. We are talking not only about physical cramping, sound exposure and the wretched appearance of five-story panel buildings, but also about urban planning blunders and short-sighted policies in the field of resettlement.

Analyzing the current state of domestic ecological housing construction, one cannot help but note the lack of an integrated approach to the use of building materials and structures in it. Until legislation and technical regulation ensure the safety of production, construction and operational processes for people and the environment, the optimal choice of environmentally friendly and resource-saving materials, products and technologies will remain the professional and civic duty of designers.

This manifests itself in many ways, for example in the case of products that do not require special care, frequent replacement and high operating costs. Thus, some scientists note that from an economic point of view, slabs made of domestic marble are a cheaper and more functional cladding for facades than paint. Painting the walls every two to three years (and this is necessary, given the climate and ecology of cities) over the 50 years of operation of the building will turn out to be more expensive than immediately decorating it with marble. And the positive effect of the fact that the toxic dye will not be produced, the painters and residents of these houses will not breathe it, its exfoliating particles will not be carried in the air and deposited on the soil and plants, is difficult to simple economic calculation.

Another example illustrating the reluctance of domestic builders and customers to count their own money and protect their health is the preferential use of imported building materials over domestic ones. Pine sheathing made at a local sawmill is economically more profitable than plywood imported from Finland, and the harm from its impact on the health of residents is obvious, since polymer resins and glue are used in the production of plywood.

In modern housing construction, materials are used that contain substances that are harmful to the health of people living in it. For example, phenol, which is used in the production of plastic (and plastic windows). The consequences of its excessive presence are very dangerous: damage to the mucous membrane and skin, the central nervous system, and reactions such as general weakness, headache, dizziness are also possible. The entry of asbestos (it is used mainly for the production of ventilation pipes and partitions) into the human body leads to cancer of the respiratory tract. Benzene and toluene, which are widely used in the paint and varnish industry, are quickly absorbed by the body during respiration, causing toxic pneumonia.

Formaldehyde, a colorless, asphyxiating gas with a pungent odor, also enters the body through the lungs. It is included in the list of carcinogenic substances, has chronic toxicity, negatively affects genetic material, reproductive organs, and has a

strong effect on the central nervous system. The source of this “wonderful” gas indoors can be wood chips, polymer materials for flooring, interior wall finishing, decorative laminated plastic, and decorative plywood.

An important problem of ensuring the environmental safety of housing under construction is the use in construction only of those building, finishing and insulating materials whose hygienic characteristics meet modern requirements. Particular attention should be paid to the need for strict adherence by manufacturing plants to the recipes and production technology adopted in official documents. Otherwise, the plant, under the brand name of a sample once approved by the sanitary service, will produce a material that can have a harmful effect on the health of residents (which has often been observed recently due to a clear trend towards the use of industrial waste in the manufacture of materials).

The use in modern housing construction of building and finishing materials, furniture, varnishes and paints that have not undergone environmental and hygienic examination causes the accumulation of a large number of pollutants in the indoor air, especially from low-quality polymer materials. Unfortunately, the most widely used polymer materials are those based on polyvinyl chloride, phenol-formaldehyde and urea-formaldehyde resins, polymethyl methacrylate, polyethylene, and polystyrene. Based on these polymer materials, linoleums and various wall and furniture coverings are made. Polymethylmethacrylate is used for the manufacture of household equipment (baths, washbasins).

Among decorative finishing materials, from our point of view, organochlorine polymers are unreasonably widely used, in particular, polyvinyl chloride, which is a product of polymerization of the monomer - vinyl chloride. Vinyl chloride in high concentrations has a narcotic and irritant effect and changes the composition of the blood. The effect of vinyl chloride vapors on the human body at high temperatures is especially unfavorable.

Conclusions. We consider the following methods for economic assessment of the quality of green housing construction to be very promising:

- general methods used at the design stage of a residential building (allow us to assess the environmental quality of a future residential building);
- private methods used at the stage of operation of a residential building (allow you to assess the environmental safety of the residential environment during the operation of the facility);
- complete methods for economic assessment of the quality of ecological housing construction (take into account all the properties characterizing the environmental quality of a residential building);
- simplified methods for economic assessment of the quality of ecological housing construction (properties characterizing the environmental quality of a residential building are taken into account selectively).

The above methods for economic assessment of the quality of ecological housing construction provide an opportunity to obtain a comprehensive quantitative assessment of the integral quality of ecological housing construction. In this case, the number of properties characterizing the environmental quality of a residential building is taken in such a way that it can be used to sufficiently fully characterize the environmental quality of any apartments.

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